

A new model of consciousness derived from black hole information paradox

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Abstract:

Panpsychism is the view that consciousness is a fundamental feature of reality. Panpsychism addresses the fact that no physical theories can ever be able to explain conscious experience in terms of physical processes. This is known as the hard problem of consciousness. However, Panpsychism does not define consciousness and the mechanism of interaction with the physical object that possess it. Hence, more details are required to incorporate it into a fully-developed theory. On the other hand, the black hole information paradox (BHIP) is a puzzle resulting from the combination of quantum mechanics and general relativity. Calculations suggest that physical information could permanently disappear in a black hole, allowing many physical states to devolve into the same state, which directly violates the laws of physics. In this work, we have attempted a new approach in which we constrained the properties of consciousness in such a way that it resolves BHIP and provides a concrete functional role of consciousness in the physical realm. We will show that this approach leads to a novel interpretation of wave function collapse and quantum entanglement. We have also suggested ways to falsify the proposed model in this work.

Keywords: Black hole, Information paradox, consciousness, panpsychism, wave function collapse

1. Background:

Panpsychism is the view that consciousness is a fundamental feature of reality [1, 2]. Basically Panpsychism addresses the fact that no physical theories can ever be able to explain conscious experience in terms of physical processes. This is known as the hard problem of consciousness [3, 4]. In the recent past, Panpsychism has become an accepted philosophical as well as scientific view to successfully explain various empirical features of consciousness [5] and certain observations in quantum mechanics [6-8]. However, Panpsychism does not define consciousness and the mechanism of interaction with the physical object that possess it [9]. Hence, more details are required to incorporate it into a fully-developed theory.

On the other hand, black hole information paradox continues to puzzle physicists for many decades. The black hole information paradox (BHIP) results from the combination of quantum mechanics and general relativity. Calculations suggest that physical information could permanently disappear in a black hole, allowing many physical states to devolve into the same state [10]. Since Hawking's initial results several exotic postulates have been proposed for solving BHIP [11-20] among which the most direct postulate is that the information is irreversibly lost [11]. This implies that the evolution of the complete system, including the black hole, is fundamentally non-unitary [11]. Such non-unitary evolution implies violation of either locality or energy-momentum conservation [21]. This constitutes what is referred to as BHIP [21]. The crux of the paradox is that if the information gets lost, it is necessary to modify quantum mechanics and if not, it is essential to modify general relativity to allow the escape of information through Hawking radiation [22]. There have been several attempts to deal with this paradox, however none of them resulting in a satisfactory solution [55, 56].

In this work, we have attempted a new approach in which we constrained the properties of consciousness in such a way that it resolves BHIP and provides a functional role of consciousness in the physical realm. This theoretical approach gives rise to a new model of consciousness potentially explaining the properties of consciousness and its mechanism of interaction with conscious and physical fields. Subsequently, we demonstrate how this derived model of consciousness can contribute to solve BHIP. We will show that this approach leads to a novel interpretation of wave function collapse and quantum entanglement. Moreover, we have suggested some specific approaches to falsify our model of consciousness on theoretical and experimental grounds.

2. Method:

A. Assumptions

Our theory is developed based on the following assumptions supported by the concept of panpsychism [1, 2]:

- a. Consciousness is a fundamental feature of reality.
- b. All physical particles in the universe possess the physical attributes (described by wave function) and the consciousness attributes.

B. Derived properties of consciousness:

Given that the above assumptions are true, BHIP can be logically resolved if consciousness has the below properties:

- a. Consciousness is the “informational” version of the quantum mechanical wave function of the associated physical object or simply the “*Informational Version of Physical (IVP)*” stored in the informational space-time. Stated differently, the attributes and content of consciousness of a particle are the particle’s physical attributes packed in an informational format and stored in the informational space-time. The informational space-time is an extra dimension that can exist in parallel with the physical dimension. One can draw an analogy to video games here. The objects in a video game obey certain physical laws in their own “informational” space-time.
- b. The informational version of the physical object cannot be destroyed by any physical process. This is in line with a postulate [23] that consciousness may exist by itself, even in the absence of matter, just like gravitational waves and excitations of space-time that may exist in the absence of protons and electrons.

By using the derived properties of consciousness, we can model various known interactions as described below:

C. Information-to-Information Interaction in informational space-time:

The combination problem of consciousness (i.e. smaller conscious entities come to constitute bigger conscious entities) [3] dictates that the information in the informational space-time of a physical object (i.e. consciousness) must possess the causal power to interact with information of other physical objects in the informational space-time. This is analogous to the objects in video games that can interact with other objects in the game. Since the “Integrated Information Theory (IIT)” of consciousness [25] is already shown to be successful in explaining the combination problem of consciousness, the IVP model must allow the formation of an integrated entity of consciousness when more than one conscious fields are interacting with each other in a maximally irreducible manner as suggested by IIT, which we can term as *maximally irreducible information complex* (MIIC). Hence, IVP model predicts that when two particles interact with each other to form a system (say atom), a *maximally irreducible information complex* (MIIC) is formed in informational space-time as a result of the interaction of the wave functions of the particles in the physical space-time. When two conscious fields are integrated in the informational space-time, the redundancy of information shared by both fields is reduced. However, it is important to note that redundancy reduction does not mean the whole became lesser than the sum of its parts. In fact, the redundancy reduction represents the level of integration in the informational space-time. This is somewhat analogous to the task of merging two essays written on two different but related topics into a single essay. The level of integration depends on the context, the topics and the way the essays were written before merging. The redundancy reduction could be a fundamental feature of informational space-time. In information theory, the measure of *redundancy* among many variables is given by the total correlation. We speculate that effectively IIT theory might be just quantifying the total correlation among the smaller conscious units. Hence, we conjecture that any mathematical algorithm that quantifies the total correlation (or lossless data compression) of two or more informational entities could be able to model how conscious fields interact with each other. There are papers attempting to model this interaction using the analogy of data compression [48, 49], which in turn validates (to an extent) the postulated properties of consciousness.

On the other hand, according to the postulated property of consciousness (derived for resolving BHIP), the content of consciousness is the informational version of the quantum mechanical wave function of the associated physical object stored in the informational space-time. Therefore, the MIIC must represent the informational version of the quantum mechanical wave function of the associated physical object in the informational space-time. It is to be noted that the quantum mechanical wave function of a system of particles is governed by the quantum field theory (QFT) [39]. This implies that the mathematical aspects of “Integrated Information Theory (IIT)” of consciousness can also be deduced from the quantum field theory (QFT) if each conscious entity is represented in the form of wave functions. An advantage of such an approach (QFT-aided wave function representation of consciousness) would be the inclusion of wave function collapse feature in the IIT framework. This assertion has some similarities with Penrose Interpretation [57]. We will explore these surprising connections between IIT, wave function collapse, Penrose Interpretation and QFT in a companion paper soon. Our proposal has some similarities with Quantum Integrated Information (QII) [40] and IVP model allows using QII framework in place of IIT. For instance, in IVP model, a single electron is supposed to have consciousness, that is, the information version of the physical. However, IIT does not allow an electron to have consciousness, whereas QII framework allows the same. Hence we find QII to be more appropriate in connection with IVP model. We believe IVP model coupled with MIIC can be used to explain how precisely smaller conscious entities give rise to higher order conscious entities (i.e. the combination problem). This approach might also help explain the empirical evidences related to the causal power of consciousness in the neuro-psychological domains [26, 27].

D. Information-to-physical Interaction in physical space-time (New interpretation for wave function collapse):

It has been postulated by many scientists that consciousness might have a functional or causal role in the *Quantum mechanics measurement problem* [7, 28-30]. This implies that the information in informational space-time must also possess a causal power in the physical space-time. According to IVP model, consciousness causes the wave function collapse. This interaction can be detailed as follows: when a higher order information entity in the informational space-time (higher Φ) interacts with a lower order information entity (lower Φ , say, an electron) in the informational space-time, the resulting Maximally Irreducible Information Complex (MIIC) in informational space-time can induce a collapse of wave function of the associated physical object in the physical space-time. Essentially, when a lower order information entity encounters a “sufficiently” higher order information entity (refer to section 4B for more details) in a MIIC-based interaction, the interaction between them will be such that there will be a net compression of the information content (due to redundancy reduction) in the lower order information entity in the informational space-time. The “compression of information” in the lower order information entity in the informational space-time causes the collapse of the physical wave function of the associated particle in the physical space-time. This process is similar to lossless data compression used in digital signal processing, wherein the information is encoded using fewer bits than the original representation. Similarly, MIIC interaction encodes the lower order information entity in a fewer bits in the informational space-time (i.e. information redundancy is minimized), which causes the collapse of the physical wave function in the physical space-time. Hence, we term this as “Lossless Information Compression (LIC)” interpretation of wave function collapse. A paper interprets the quantum probability as optimal data compression [50]. However, this paper [50] does not interpret the collapse itself as data compression and is very different from our proposal in terms of its foundational and functional aspects. Another paper attempts to measure the integrated information based on the “lossless data compression” model [48]. Our proposal only extends the “lossless data compression” model [48] to the next level and connects it with the wave function collapse. Moreover, our interpretation is in line with “consciousness causes collapse” interpretation for the quantum mechanics measurement problem [7, 8, 41-44]. The LIC interpretation clearly takes away the need for a human element to collapse the wave function in line with some recent proposals [8, 40, 41, 44, 58, 62]. An important feature of LIC interpretation is that it might allow calculating the precise condition (i.e. Φ_{\min}) needed for the wave function collapse of a physical system by using the mathematical framework offered by IIT and lossless data compression techniques. Moreover, LIC model suggests that the so-called “quantum jumps” may not be instantaneous but happen as a smooth transition through a series of superposition states, which is inline with “Quantum Trajectory Theory” (QTT) [62].

E. Informational Entanglement in informational space-time (New interpretation for entanglement):

Quantum entanglement is a physical phenomenon that occurs when a pair or group of particles are generated, interact, or share spatial proximity in a way such that the quantum state of each particle of the pair or group cannot be described independently of the state of the others, including when the particles are separated by a large distance. Though quantum entanglement has been proven experimentally, the mechanism behind it (i.e. how particles far apart linked to each other) remains a mystery and there is no reasonable explanation for this phenomenon till date. IVP model includes informational entanglement in informational space-time because the entanglement interaction of physical objects in the physical space-time is an established phenomenon [31]. This implies that physically separated (i.e. separated by large spatial distance) informational entities associated with different physical objects can also form MIIC from distance in the informational space-time. According to IVP model, entanglement can be detailed as follows: Let us consider two persons, Person A and Person B, who happen to meet each other in a specific physical space-time coordinate. Let us also assume that they share information about each other when they meet and then start moving away in physical space-time. Though they are physically separated, they still “know” each other regardless of their current position in physical space-time. In other words, though their coordinates have changed in physical space-time, they remain in the same coordinate in the informational space-time. This implies that “knowing” is space-time invariant or simply nonlocal in nature. This shows that nonlocality is the basic feature of informational space-time, not of physical space-time. This idea has similarities with another proposal called Hyperdimension [54]. Now let us consider an entangled pair of particles (i.e. both particles “know” the information of each other). Assume that the wave function of the first particle is collapsed as described in the previous section. This means that a higher order information entity has compressed the information of the first particle in informational space-time that resulted in the collapse of the first particle in physical space-time. Due to the nonlocal nature of informational space-time, the information associated with the entangled particle (i.e. the second particle) is also simultaneously compressed in informational space-time (regardless of how far it is from the first particle in physical space-time), though there is no direct interaction taking place between them in physical space-time. This process has many similarities with what is known as “predictive information transfer” – if A has causal effect on B, knowing A might help you know what B might do later in time without the need for a direct physical linkage [41]. The exact connection between LIC-based quantum entanglement and predictive information transfer will be explored in another paper. There is another similar conjecture that consciousness is non-local quantum information with a status equal to energy, matter, and space-time [45]. In general, our proposal is in consensus with the notion that entanglement has something to do with information. We argue that (a) nonlocality is a fundamental feature in the informational space-time, which only manifests in the physical space-time via entanglement and wave function collapse and (b) quantum entanglement is one of the evidences for the existence of the postulated informational space-time (an extra dimension).

3. Solving BHIP using IVP model of consciousness:

According to IVP model, a particle (or any physical system) can be completely described by (μ, Φ, Ψ) . Here μ denotes the informational version of the physical wave function of the particle in informational space-time, Φ denotes the corresponding “integrated information” in informational space-time and Ψ denotes the physical wave function of the particle in physical space-time. According to the postulates of IVP model, the μ component and the Φ component of the particle can exist even in the absence of its Ψ component. Hence, the unitary evolution of the wave function of a fallen physical object inside the black hole can continue in the universe if the interactions explained above are taking place. We conjecture two possible ways of solving BHIP using IVP model:

Possibility 1: Let us assume that a particle P1 has fallen inside black hole at time t . The wave function of the particle is $\psi_1(x,t)$ and the information of the particle in informational space-time is $\mu_1(x,t)$. That is, $\mu_1(x,t)$ represents $\psi_1(x,t)$ in the informational space-time. Also assume that the information of the particle (μ_1) has interacted with the information of another particle P2 present outside the black hole ($\mu_2(x, t-\Delta t)$) and formed an entanglement pair (refer to section 2E) before the particle has fallen inside the black hole (i.e. at $t-\Delta t$). As mentioned before, $\mu_1(x,t)$ still survives inside the black hole (though $\psi_1(x,t)$ is lost permanently) and because of its entanglement with P2 outside black hole, $\mu_1(x,t)$ is teleported outside of the black hole and integrated with $\mu_2(x, t)$ according to MIIC mechanism (refer to section 2C). Subsequently, due to the altered information associated with P2, $\psi_2(x,t)$ is accordingly modified (refer to section 2D), which might also result in a collapse if conditions for LIC is met (i.e. Φ_{\min}). The postulated

teleportation of information in the informational space-time is analogous to the teleportation of energy via entanglement from distance in the physical space-time [34]. The proposed approach has similarities with another recent proposal, wherein the quantum entanglement acts like a bridge to teleport information out of black hole [35]. There are similarities with other proposal that connects BHIP with consciousness-based interpretation of wave function collapse [59].

Possibility 2: Very recently, some theoretical advancements have been reported that indicate that there could be a continuous interplay between hawking radiation and the interior of the black hole itself and as the black hole evaporates, the interior begins to contain information that can be correlated to the outgoing radiation [10, 51, 52]. However, physicists agree that the central puzzle (that is, how the information can get out of the black hole) remains unsolved by these recent postulates. A collection of criticisms on these proposals can be found here [53]. Motivated by these ideas and criticisms, we speculate another possibility that the “orphaned” information $\mu_1(x,t)$ might get entangled with the outgoing Hawking radiation as suggested by the recent papers [10, 51, 52] and possibly get out of black hole. Moreover, we argue that the interactions of the kind suggested in these recent papers could be an indication for the existence of a deeper hidden dimension governed solely by information.

4. Means of falsification:

The proposed model can be falsified on the theoretical and experimental grounds with the help of the blow suggested approaches.

A. Combination problem:

At the core, IIT theory of consciousness fails to explain why there is “integrated information” in first place. According to IVP model, consciousness is the informational version of physical stored in the informational space-time. Equating consciousness to a piece of information representing the underlying physical object helps explain why “integration” is an essential feature of consciousness. As mentioned before, the integrated information could be the result of one of the fundamental features of the informational space-time, namely, “redundancy reduction”. Hence, IVP model and IIT theory are substantiating each other.

Most importantly, IVP model suggests additional ways to simulate the interaction of conscious fields (calculating total correlations, data compression model and QFT model). For instance, a significant computational challenge in calculating integrated information is finding the Minimum Information Partition (MIP) of a neural system, which requires iterating through all possible network partitions. It was shown that the spectral decomposition of the correlation matrix of a system's dynamics is a quick proxy for MIP [47]. The proposed theoretical framework of modeling the interaction as lossless data compression coupled with wave function collapse (can be modeled using QFT) might act as a robust proxy for MIP calculation. An advantage of the suggested new proxy for MIP calculation over the existing proxies would be the inclusion of wave function collapse in the calculations.

In addition, IVP model predicts that the formation of MIIC due to the interaction of conscious fields might not happen in a single step, but involve a series of intermediate steps. Essentially IVP model predicts that the “quantum jump” (i.e. integrating multiple conscious fields into single field in a single step) is not possible because there is no way such a process can happen without involving one or more feedback loops measuring the fitness of the integration. This prediction is sharply in contrast with IIT.

The mathematical aspects of these predictions will be detailed in a separate paper soon. Surprisingly, another recent paper models consciousness itself as data compression [49], which only substantiates IVP model of consciousness.

B. Wave function collapse and quantum entanglement:

An important aspect of IVP model is the postulated existence of informational space-time. It is still not very clear how a space-time made only of information will behave and interact within itself and with physical space-time. However, one can speculate that “redundancy reduction” can be one of the basic features of informational space-time, which could lead to wave function collapse. Another basic feature of informational space-time could be its nonlocality. These two postulated features of informational space-time gives rise to a new interpretation for the two most puzzling aspects of quantum mechanics: wave function collapse and quantum entanglement. Especially the LIC interpretation of wave function collapse provides a new mathematical framework for the wave function collapse as supported by other related work [48].

One way could be that we can calculate an improved version of “ Φ -density” [8] using LIC model and use it in the following collapse equation suggested by Chalmers [8]:

$$d\psi_t = \left[-\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{H} dt + \sqrt{\lambda} \int d^N q (\hat{\phi}(\mathbf{q}) - \langle \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{q}) \rangle_t) dW_t(\mathbf{q}) - \frac{\lambda}{2} \int d^N q \int d^N r \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{r}) (\hat{\phi}(\mathbf{q}) - \langle \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{q}) \rangle_t) (\hat{\phi}(\mathbf{r}) - \langle \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{r}) \rangle_t) dt \right] \psi_t.$$

Here Ψ_t is the wave function state at t ; H_0 is the Hamiltonian; λ representing collapse rate; W_t is the noise function; \mathbf{G} is the spatial correlation function that determines the shape of collapse behavior and Φ is the collapse operator.

According to LIC, when a particle P (a lower order information entity (Φ_{low})) encounters a physical system S (a sufficiently higher order information entity (Φ_{high})), the information (μ) belonging to the particle is encoded in a lower number of bits ($\mu_{\text{compressed}}$) in the informational space-time, which causes the collapse of the wave function (Ψ) of the particle. Hence, the Φ -density parameter in the above equation will be based on Φ_{low} and Φ_{high} . There should be a threshold (Φ_{min}) information content required for the physical system in order to transform the particle’s μ into $\mu_{\text{compressed}}$ in a lossless manner. We conjecture that if Φ of the physical system is lower than Φ_{min} , it will not be able to transform μ into $\mu_{\text{compressed}}$ in a lossless manner and therefore collapse cannot happen. Stated differently, when the particle being observed “knows” that its information can be compressed by the physical system (observer) in a lossless manner in the informational space-time, it will collapse in the physical space-time.

Moreover, the LIC model predicts that the collapse may not be instantaneous and might involve a series of intermediate steps as the underlying “compression of information” in the informational space-time itself will be happening at a specific rate involving definite steps as mentioned before in section 4A. The collapse rate can be theoretically calculated by applying the data compression method. This aspect of the proposed LIC model of collapse is in agreement with “Quantum Trajectory Theory” (QTT) [62] and some latest experimental findings [63].

In principle, the Φ_{min} required to compress the information of a given physical entity characterized by its state parameters (μ , Ψ , Φ) can be derived by using the mathematical framework offered by IIT to calculate MIP. We can also use the model proposed in [58] to develop our proposal. Moreover, we speculate that the methods proposed in [40] can also be leveraged to falsify our model. A detailed theoretical account on this aspect will be explored in our next communication.

Though there is an attempt to link the quantum probability to data compression [50], to the best of our knowledge, there are no papers that interpret the wave function collapse itself as lossless data compression. We speculate that LIC model of collapse can predict specific collapse properties such as collapse rate (λ), threshold Φ (Φ -density) required for collapse and other physical conditions for collapse. Establishing a connection between wave function collapse and data compression could directly imply that (a) consciousness collapses wave function under certain conditions and (b) consciousness obeys informational principles when interacting with physical – which implies that consciousness itself could be an informational version of the physical. Therefore, establishing the connection between wave function collapse and data compression is a specific way to falsify the proposed IVP model of consciousness.

5. Other Predictions/Speculations:

The IVP model of consciousness also leads to some new predictions described below. Please note that these are mere speculations and detailed research is needed to strengthen the below predictions.

A. Explaining Target Morphology:

We speculate that the IVP model can also help explain some puzzles in biology. For instance, IVP model can possibly explain the puzzles surrounding target morphology [41]. A surgically removed portion of liver will eventually regrow to its normal size. The puzzle here is that how the newly generated liver cells know the final size and shape [41]. We speculate that IVP model might solve this puzzle. According to IVP model, the informational version of a physical object is never destroyed. When the portion of the liver is surgically removed, the informational version of the removed portion is still entangled to the rest of the liver. When the new cells are generated, there can possibly be some sort of wave function collapse in the appropriate spatial locations due to the interaction of new cells with the informational version of the removed cells, which can guide the new cells how to grow, where to grow and when or where to stop.

B. Hyperconstructalization:

We speculate that there will be a tendency in time for the emergence of design patterns in informational space-time involving informational entities (quantified by Φ) associated with physical entities. This hypothesized tendency for the emergence of design patterns in informational space-time is termed as “Hyperconstructalization”. This hypothesis entails that constructal law [46] can be applied (probably in a modified form) to explain the design formation in informational space-time.

I argue that the emergence of design patterns in physical space-time can be a manifestation of Hyperconstructalization in informational space-time and there can be possibly many more implications or manifestations of Hyperconstructalization in the physical space-time.

I argue that nature could have used Hyperconstructalization to evolve various complex design patterns in a shorter time. For instance, the permutations and combinations for arriving at the design of the first DNA molecule could have happened in the informational space-time and later manifested in the physical space-time.

I also argue that nature could have used Hyperconstructalization to build certain important physical configurations faster and better, instead of building them from the scratch, possibly leading to an accelerated evolution. This implies that Hyperconstructalization could be making the cosmos more intelligent in terms of evolving useful design patterns over time.

An analogy for such improvements mediated via Hyperconstructalization could be seen in a Wikipedia page. Assume that one wants to build a new Wikipedia page about quantum mechanics from the scratch. Due to the abundance of information, it will be very time consuming and less efficient to build such a web page from the scratch. Instead, one would prefer using hypertexts to make the page more crisp and clear without losing the essential information.

Possibly, the hypothesized Hyperconstructalization could just be serving like those hypertexts in the wiki page in the informational space-time when forming newer design patterns. The hypothesized Hyperconstructalization can possibly explain the origin of organized information and evolutionary biology.

C. Gravity and Dark Energy:

Recently there have been alternative interpretations for gravity that connect gravity with entropy [60]. In this paper [60], it is argued that gravity is a consequence of the “information associated with the positions of material bodies”. Hence we strongly speculate that there can be a deeper connection between IVP model of consciousness and gravity. Similarly, there are no satisfactory and consistent explanations for the existence of Dark energy [61]. We speculate that IVP model can be used to explain dark energy as well due to its connection with gravity and black hole.

6. Discussion:

The motivation for us to use consciousness as the candidate to solve BHIP is four-fold. First, the common thread between consciousness and BHIP is information. Second, there is a growing consensus on the unexplainability of hard problem of consciousness, which hints at the possibility that consciousness could indeed be a fundamental feature of reality alongside the physical. Third, the puzzles in quantum mechanics such as wave function collapse and entanglement hints at an information-governed universe and a larger and inevitable role of consciousness in explaining them. Fourth, there is an increasing criticism from the physics fraternity [53] on the validity of the recent theoretical proposals for solving BHIP.

Our basic argument is that a particle (or any physical system) cannot be completely described if its informational components (μ , Φ) are neglected. We have shown two distinct ways in which BHIP can be solved by including the informational components in the description of the particle. We have shown how redundancy reduction and nonlocality can act as the underlying mechanisms for all the interactions in informational space-time and manifest in physical space-time. The basic assumptions leveraged in the proposed approach are (a) panpsychism is true and (b) consciousness has the postulated properties. The proposed theoretical approach of constraining the properties of consciousness for solving BHIP is unique and offers the following advantages: (a) This approach bridges two staggeringly different topics (Panpsychism and Black holes) and gives a new theoretical framework to solve BHIP; (b) It provides a new interpretation for the most puzzling aspects of quantum mechanics, namely, wave function collapse and quantum entanglement; (c) It describes the combination problem of consciousness in terms of new mathematical model in conjunction with IIT and (d) It possibly explains the puzzles surrounding certain biological phenomenon.

In 1994, a paper highlighted striking similarities between the information lost in black hole and the possible occurrence of the same in conscious beings [24]. Also, the idea that consciousness exists in a separate space-time dimension is not new and proposed by many scientists and philosophers [36-38, 54], however the difference here is the idea that the content of consciousness must comprise (in order to avoid BHIP) the quantum mechanical wave function of its physical object. In 1986, a researcher proposed that consciousness can be represented as “probability-of-experience” or as a wave function in consciousness space-time [38]. The author went on to construct a wave function equation for consciousness that used attributes like mass, charge, momentum just like a usual quantum mechanical wave function. However those attributes of consciousness mentioned by the author (mass, charge, momentum, etc) were different from the physical ones and were given a different ontological meaning altogether, which sharply differentiates my proposal from this one. Moreover, my proposal is that consciousness is the wave function of the physical object wrapped in an informational format in the informational space-time, which will not replace the wave function of the physical object in the physical format in the physical space-time. In other words, the physical particle will always have both wave functions (informational and physical) in two different space-time dimensions.

A limitation of IVP model is that it does not offer any solution to the hard problem of consciousness as it is directly derived from Panpsychism [4]. The hard problem can be simply summarized by the following two questions: (a) why does all information processing need to feel like anything from the inside? and (b) Why do we have experience at all? IVP model does not give answers to these two questions. In other words, IVP model does not explain how phenomenal aspects of consciousness arise from the information stored in the informational space-time. However, the view behind IVP model of consciousness is different from other prominent views such as Physicalism, Dualism and Russellian Panpsychism [1, 33] and might offer a number of advantages. For instance, IVP model can contribute to solve the combination problem (where Russellian Panpsychism fails) [33] and the proposed interactions (2C, 2D and 2E) can help explain various features of consciousness.

The IVP model of consciousness demands the existence of an extra dimension parallel to the physical to contain the information. As compared to the other postulates [11-20] that attempt to resolve BHIP, the proposed one is more direct and possibly has wider implications in the field of science and philosophy. Though the model does not implicate any direct change in the theory of quantum mechanics and general theory of relativity, it calls for an extension of these theories to understand the nature of consciousness. The IVP model gives a view that the content of consciousness may not be different from the physical, however stored in a different dimension. One might argue that it could be very difficult to encode a huge amount of information about a physical object in the informational space-time. One

explanation for this argument can be drawn from the historical evolution of hard drives to store information. The amount of information that can be stored per unit volume is increasing in an exponential order. Hence, it can be asserted that the nature could have already found a most efficient way to encode a gargantuan of information per unit volume. This assertion is inspired from self-simulation hypothesis [32].

7. Conclusion:

We have derived a new Panpsychism-based model of consciousness by constraining its properties in order to solve BHIP. We have also suggested ways to falsify the model in this work. Moreover, IVP model makes some predictions in the fields beyond physics, suggesting a need for a broader outlook on these topics, which might possibly lead to some technological advancements in the future. We speculate that the inclusion of IVP model with IIT can elevate our understanding about consciousness. Our future research will mainly focus on the following aspects: (a) justifying the model with the support of an elaborate mathematical framework (b) explaining the empirical features of consciousness using the new model, (c) methods to theoretically and experimentally test the model, and (d) exploring possible applications of the model.

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